

Training Material For MAMMOth created by the RUG

AI Biases with Ari

Purpose: supporting AI literacy development

Audience: children (4-12 years old)

Medium: exhibit with printed posters

Duration: ~15 minutes

Support level: according to group size

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Short Description: Targeting a population that is often neglected in AI ethics dissemination, the RUG has created an exhibition aimed at children. A combination of interactive posters, comics, and decoder glasses provide an interactive, easy-to-understand, and most importantly, age-appropriate introduction to AI and AI biases.

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Notes:

- The supplementary handbook and promotional text are available